

Sedimentological analysis by A.Baud

1. Wadi Musjah

Cycle 1 about 1m thick, comprises a lower red ammonoid limestone part (level A) and an upper light beige bivalve coquina cemented biostrome (level B). The irregular dissolution boundary between the level A and B (supplementary fig. 1) is due to strong pressure solution. The microfacies of level A consist of bioclastic partly recrystallized lime mud, with packed, partly crushed bivalve shells surrounded of ammonoid shells, peloides, rare bryozoan and echinoid spines. The microfacies of the light beige bivalve coquina (level B) consists of well sorted bioclastic, small sized monospecific bivalve tests (millimetric), in a blocky calcite cement matrix.

The Cycle 2, 0.9 m thick, illustrated in supplementary fig. 2, comprises, as cycle 1, a lower bivalve rich red ammonoid limestone part (level C) and an upper light beige bivalve coquina cemented biostrome (level D). The microfacies of the red limestone shows a well sorted bioclastic packed short sized (millimetric) monospecific bivalve tests in red lime mud and bioclastic lime mud, with packed, partly crushed bivalve shells within some ammonoid shells. It is interesting to note that the ammonoid samples WM 8 of Brühwiler et al. (2012) with *Inyoites oweni* is coming from level C and was analyzed for further studies on the ammonoid shell structure (Klug 2007). The microfacies of the light beige bivalve coquina (level D) is a well sorted bioclastic short-sized monospecific bivalve tests (millimetric) in a calcite cemented matrix.

The Cycle 3, 0.5 m thick comprises, as the two previous cycles, a lower red ammonoid limestone part (level E) and an upper light gray bivalve coquina cemented biostrome with some brachiopod shells (level F). The microfacies of level E consist of bioclastic lime mud, with packed, partly crushed bivalve shells within ammonoid shells (supplementary fig. 2 E). From this level is the Bruehwiler et al. (2012) ammonoid level WM 7 with a *Juvenites* fauna. Brachiopod shells appear in the upper light gray bivalve coquina.

The Cycle 4, 0.5 m thick, is showing the sudden crinoidal invasion with ossicles deposited in rose lime mud (level G) followed by a light gray brachiopod coquina cemented biostrome (level H). The microfacies of the crinoidal limestone consist of a bioclastic crinoidal packstone with brachiopod and bivalve crushed tests, ostracods and mini foraminifera showing partly cemented laminae in dark red lime muddy matrix, partly recrystallized (supplementary fig. 3). The *Anasibirites* ammonoid fauna was found from level G.

The Cycle 5, 1.3 m thick, consist of a thick bioclastic lime mud slightly recrystallized with crinoids, brachiopods levels and rare unidentifiable ammonoids, followed by light bioclastic, high-energy crinoidal cemented grainstone. The microfacies of the bioclastic red limestone (level I) shows brachiopod shells in a lime muddy matrix with bivalve crushed tests, ostracods and some crinoid

ossicles; but also crinoidal limestone and some sponge fibers of crushed sponge bodies can be found (see supplementary fig. 4).

The microfacies of the overlying high energy light rose crinoidal limestone (encrinites) (level J) shows densely packed crinoidal ossicles and spines in cemented matrix with brachiopod and bivalve crushed tests, ostracods and rare intraclasts.

The base of Cycle 6, 0.5m, is visible and consists of a bioclastic lime mud with brachiopod rich levels, crinoids, and crushed thin shelled bivalves. The microfacies (level K) shows full brachiopod sections in a dark lime muddy matrix with thin bivalve shells, ostracods, crinoid ossicles and small sized foraminifers.

2. Jebel Aweri

2.1 Lower block, description of lower block (parts A – C)

The lower part A (see fig. 3) consists of five cycles of shell supported biostrome and clast supported bioherm succession

Cycle 1, 1.1m thick comprises a lower shell supported biostrome part and an upper bioherm part with the following microfacies of cycle 1a and cycle 1b. Cycle 1a consists of a bivalve shells boundstone with early diagenetic cement. Microfacies of cycle 1b consists of a dendrolitic stromatolite with a “cloudy” appearance of the 2-3mm spaced microbial crust and a dendrolite boundstone (supplementary fig. 8 A, B).

Cycle 2, 2.9m thick, is made of thin bedded, coquinite at the base and the bioherm consists of dendrolitic type stromatolite similar to cycle 1. The microfacies consists of a dendrolitic stromatolite, with microconchids and possible bryozoans in cycle 2a and microbial peloid boundstone with microconchids, stromatactis and possible sponge fibers in cycle 2b.

Cycle 3, 2.5m thick, consists of a basal coquinite biostrome (3a) and a bioherm made of boundstone clasts coated by syndimentary radial-fibrous cement. (supplementary fig. 7 A -E, part of 3b).

Cycle 4, 1.7m thick, is made of thin bedded, coquinite at the base (microfacies of cycle 4a, a cemented bivalve coquina, supplementary fig. 5 E) followed by well laminated stromatolite with domal and partly broken structures (supplementary fig. 6 A). The microfacies of cycle 4b shows millimetric contorted dark laminae belonging to dendrolitic stromatolite (supplementary fig. 6 B, C).

Cycle 5, 1.8m thick, consists of well bedded coquinite at the base (microfacies of cycle 5a, supplementary fig. 5 C) cemented stacked bivalve shells and dark intraclasts surrounded by yellowish fibrous calcite cement followed by light calcite needles (former aragonite?), and of a bioherm made dendrolite boundstone with rare bioclastes (cycle 5b).

The biostrome middle part (B) consists of a lower bivalve shell accumulations Level 6) (supplementary. fig. 5 A) followed by a brachiopod shell level 7 and a mixed bivalve and brachiopod shell accumulations (level 8, supplementary. fig. 5 D).

Level 6: 5.2 m thick, consists of cemented stacked bivalve shells (supplementary. fig. 5 B).

Level 7, 0.8m thick, is made of a cemented brachiopod accumulation and the microfacies shows the radial-fibrous cement surrounding the brachiopod shell and empty space filled by dark lime mud.

Level 8, 3m thick, consists of cemented stacked bivalve shells comprising two main levels 0.5 m thick richer in brachiopods, one about one meter above the level 7 and the second at the top. The microfacies of level 8 (illustrated in the supplementary material) is showing cemented and encrusted stacked bivalve shells and rare crinoid ossicles.

Part C consists of the bioherm top with lime clasts (level 9). Level 9, 2.2m thick, is showing an apparently erosive base over the shell level 8.

The base of level 9 consists of lime clast with a thrombolytic type of microbialite and a colony of possible sponge bodies with radial-fibrous cement filling stromatactis voids. The microfacies shows, as in cycle 3, many boundstone clasts (here possible sponge bodies) coated by syndimentary radial-fibrous cement (lower part of level 9), and an upper part mainly of centimetric to decimetric lime clasts surrounded by microbial peloid boundstone with bioclasts and crinoid ossicles supplementary. fig. 8 E, F).

2.2 Description of the upper block (parts D-F)

The upper block, early Spathian in age, is more diversified and subdivided in 6 levels (10-15), with a shell supported biostrome base, a bioherm with clasts upper part and a top characterized by a crinoidal biostrome, overlaid by red lime mudstone.

Part D (=Level 10), 1m thick, is similar to level 7 and consists of a biostrome of stacked, cemented brachiopod shells with preserved shell structure surrounded by fibrous calcite cement within an incrustated grainstone matrix and crinoid ossicles.

Part E consists of level 11-13. Level 11, 2m thick, consists of a biohermal microbial peloid boundstone with bioclasts and crinoid ossicles. Level 12, 1.8m thick, is a bioherm with the microfacies showing a peloid microclotted dendrolite type of microbialite. Level 13, 2m thick, consists partly of clasts coated by syndimentary radial-fibrous cement with voids of stromatactis type filled by fibrous calcite cement (supplementary. fig. 8 C). The microfacies is showing a reef clast with the coating of syndimentary fibrous calcite (fc) cement (supplementary. fig. 8 D).

The uppermost part F consists of level 14 and 15). Level 14, 0.3m thick, consists of a crinoidal biostrome, with the microfacies showing a microbial stabilized peloid grainstone with crinoid ossicles, echinoid spines, microforaminifera, and rare fragmented bivalve and brachiopod shells

Level 15, 0.3m visible, is a rose-colored lime mudstone, Hallstatt type (supplementary. fig. 8 G).

References

- BRÜHWILER, T., BUCHER, H., GOUEMAND, N. & GALFETTI, T. 2012. Smithian (Early Triassic) ammonoid faunas from Exotic Blocks from Oman: taxonomy and biochronology. *Palaeontographica Abteilung – Paläozoologie-Stratigraphie* 296, 3-107.
- KLUG, C., BRÜHWILER, T., KORN, D., SCHWEIGERT, G., BRAYARD, A. AND TILSLEY, J., 2007. Ammonoid shell structures of primary organic composition. *Palaeontology*, 50(6), pp.1463-1478. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-4983.2007.00722.x>

Figures

Supplementary figure 1 : Wadi Musjah; A: outcrop view of the red ammonoid limestone level A, base of the outcrop. **B:** Microfacies (level A, WM8iso, bioclastic recrystallized limestone with packed, partly crushed bivalve shells within ammonoid shells, peloides, intraclasts and echinid spines (scale bar=1mm). **C:** outcrop view of part of Cycle 1, with the contact between the red ammonoid limestone level A and the beige bivalve coquina cemented biostrome level B. **D:** Microfacies (from level B, between WM iso 11 and WM iso 12), bioclastic limestone with calcite cemented packed, millimetric, thin shelled bivalves (biostrome, scale bar=1mm).

Supplementary figure 2: Wadi Musjah; **A:** outcrop view of Cycle 2, with the contact between the red ammonoid limestone level C and the beige bivalve coquina cemented biostrome level D; **B:** Microfacies from level D (WM iso 16), bioclastic limestone with calcite cemented packed, millimetric, thin shelled bivalves (biostrome); **C:** Microfacies from level C (WM iso 15), bioclastic lime mud with packed, thin shelled bivalve and some ammonoid shells (scale bar=1mm). **D:** outcrop view of Cycle 3, with the contact between the red ammonoid limestone level E and the gray bivalve-brachiopod coquina cemented biostrome level F; **E:** Microfacies from top of level E (WM iso 20), bioclastic lime mud slightly recrystallized with ammonoid shells and thin shelled bivalve (scale bar=1mm). **F:** detail of microfacies from top of level E (WM iso 20).

Supplementary figure 3: Wadi Musjah; A: outcrop view of Cycle 4, with the contact between the rosa coloured crinoidal limestone level G and the gray brachiopod coquina cemented biostrome level H; **B:** Microfacies from upper part of unit G (WM iso 23), bioclastic crinoidal lime packstone (scale bar=1mm). Figure 9, **C:** outcrop view of lower part (level I) of Cycle 5, showing the contacts with the underlying level H and the overlying level J. **D=**Microfacies from lower part of level I (WM iso 26), bioclastic lime packstone with preseved brachiopods and gastropods shells, crushed thin shelled bivalve and crinoid ossicles in a lime muddy matrix; **E=** Microfacies from middle part of level I (WM iso 28), bioclastic crinoidal lime packstone, with bivalve crushed tests, ostracodes and fibers of crushed sponges; **F=** Microfacies from upper part of level I, bioclastic crinoidal lime wackestone, with some crushed bivalve tests, fibers of crushed sponges and dark coloured intraclast; **G=** Microfacies from middle part of level I (WM 3 C), bioclastic limestone with recrystallized brachiopod shells, crushed thin shelled bivalve and crinoid ossicles in a lime muddy matrix (scale bar=1mm).

Supplementary figure 4: Wadi Musjah; A: outcrop view of the upper part (level J) of Cycle 5, with apparently crossbedded, light bioclastic, high energy crinoidal cemented grainstone. Microfacies: **B=** Microfacies from lower part of level J (WM iso 30), bioclastic crinoidal grainstone, with brachiopod and bivalve crushed tests, ostracodes and rare intraclasts; **C=** Microfacies from middle part of level J (WM 23 C), bioclastic grainstone with brachiopod and bivalve crushed tests, ostracode, crinoidal ossicles and spines, peloides and small intraclasts in calcite cemented matrix. **D=**enlargement of fig. 4.C (scale bar=1mm). **E:** outcrop view of the lower part (level K) of Cycle 6, showing the contacts with the underlying level J and a brachiopod abundance at the base, Microfacies: **F=** Microfacies from lower part of level K (WM 25 C), bioclastic brachiopod packstone with small bivalve shells, ostracodes, crinoides ossicles and mini-foraminifera in a dark lime muddy matrix; **G=** Microfacies from upper part of level J (WM 26 C), bioclastic packstone with crushed brachiopod and bivalves tests and crinoides ossicles; **H=**enlargement of fig. 4F; (scale bar=1mm).

Supplementary figure 5: Jebel Aweri; A: outcrop view of a bivalve biostrome (level 6). **B:** polished surface of the biostrome, level 6. **C:** microfacies of level 5a; **D:** microfacies of level 8; **E:** microfacies of level 4a (scale bar=1mm).

Supplementary figure 6: Jebel Aweri; A: outcrop view of level 4b with horizontal and domal stromatolite structures. **B and C:** microfacies showing dendrolitic stromatolite with a “cloudy” appearance of the 2-3mm spaced microbial crusts (both from level 4b, scale bar=1mm).

Supplementary figure 7: Jebel Aweri; A level 3b: outcrop view of reef clasts surrounded by fibrous calcite cement and voids filled by blocky calcite. **B:** clasts surrounded by fibrous calcite cement and voids filled by concentric and botroidal calcite cement. **C and D:** clasts surrounded by fibrous calcite cement. **E:** spheres in the "fibrous" cement. (scale bar=1mm.).

Supplementary figure 8: Jebel Aweri; A: bivalve shells boundstone with early diagenetic cement, from level 1b. **B:** dentrolitic stromatolite with a “cloudy” appearance of the 2-3mm spaced microbial crust from level 1b, scale bar=1mm). **C:** Outcrop view of part of level 13 with some reef clast (rc) and fibrous cement (fc). **D:** microfacies of level 13 with part of a reef clast surrounded by a millimeter thick syndepositional radial-fibrous cement (fc). Possible sponge tissue (sp) in the upper part left. **E** (part of the view of fig. 8F): outcrop view of the base of the bioherm level 9 with a thrombolite type of microbialite and possible sponge bodies surrounded by light radialfibrous cement filling also voids (possible crushed sponge bodies). **F:** outcrop view of the boundary between the top of the shell supported biostrome level 8 and the base of the clast supported bioherm level 9 with heterogeneous sized lime clasts in a calcite cement matrix (rectangle corresponds to fig. 8E view). **G:** microfacies of level 15 showing a microbial stabilized peloid grainstone with crinoid ossicles, echinid spines, microforaminifera, and rare fragmented bivalve and brachiopod shells. (scale bar=1mm).